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BIOBASED GLASS FIBER SIZINGS FOR DEGRADABLE COMPOSITES IN MEDICAL AND TECHNICAL APPLICATIONS

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Biomaterials and Biocomposites

- Biomaterials:
Ceramics, Polymers and **Glasses**
- Foundation for novel biocomposites:
bioactive glasses

→ osteoinductive, osteoconductive

→ Our aim: novel biodegradable load-bearing composite materials

Bioactive glass as granules

Melt spinning process

Bioactive glass as endless fiber

Novel Biocomposite Materials - Sizing

Sizing the property-decisive interface

- Biobased + degradable
- 1) Increase tensile strength
 - 2) Protection of the fiber
 - 3) Fiber-matrix-adhesion

My aim: development and analysis of a suitable biodegradable and biobased sizing for degradable glass fibers

Materials – Glasses and Sizing Components

Glasses

parts	E-Glass M.-%	45S5 M.-%	18-06 M.-%
SiO ₂	53	45	65
Al ₂ O ₃	15	-	-
P ₂ O ₅	-	6	0
B ₂ O ₃	5	-	1,5
Na ₂ O	-	24	18,4
K ₂ O	-	-	-
CaO	19	24	15,0
MgO	4	-	0,1

Spinning trials

Dip coating trials

Sizing: Water based

Bio based film formers

Chitosan

Starch

Silane coupling agents

GPTMS – Epoxy silane

N-(2-Aminoethyl)-3-APTMS - Diaminosilane

Workflow – Fiber Processing and Investigation

- Thermal properties of films
- SEM/EDX
- Single Fiber Tensile test (SFT)

- Sizing Content
- SEM/EDX
- Single Fiber Tensile test (SFT)
- Roving Tensile test (RT)

Composite manufacturing of unidirectional plates by winding with PLA filaments

→ Transverse and longitudinal strength

Melt Spinning of Fibers

Results – Thermal Properties and Sizing Content

- Macroscopic films:
 - Homogeneous film forming observed
 - Thermal stability over 200°C for all film formers
- Sizing content was determined gravimetrically

Results – Sizing Characterization - SEM/EDX

Results – Single Fiber Tensile Tests

Objective: increase of single fiber tensile strength through the sizing

Weibull-distribution:

- 50 samples measured
- Probability of failure (P) is assigned to every fracture strength (σ)

$$P = 1 - e^{-\left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0}\right)^m}$$

- **Weibull modulus m**
= homogeneity of distribution of flaws in the glass fibre network
- **Weibull characteristic strength σ_0**
= 63,2% of fibres break at this value

Results – Single Fiber Tensile Tests

Objective: increase of single fiber tensile strength through the sizing

Dip-coating Pre-trial - 18-06

Fibre Drawing - E-Glass

Results – Roving Tensile Tests on E-Glass

Objectives: filament-to-filament adhesion, transmission of force

Two effects strengthen the yarn:

- *On fiber scale:*
healing of defects by silane
- *On yarn scale:*
filament-to-filament adhesion by film formers
- Good filament-to-filament adhesion on the yarn with bio based film formers

Feel and condition of the yarn:

When bio based film formers applied

- + yarn closure – no splicing
- + processability – easy to pull from the spool

Results – Composite Manufacturing and Tensile Testing

Objectives: filament-to-matrix adhesion, protection of the fiber through sizing, yarn closure/processability

Summary and Outlook

- Improvements in tensile strength, fiber matrix adhesion and processability
 - Simple and biobased sizing formula
- Publication in progress
including spinning of bioactive glass fibres

Next steps:

- Optimize sizing (further film formers, tailor amount of all components) and spool geometry for better processability
- Go into application (medical or technical)

Thank you!

Contact

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